

QUANTIFYING THE SHEAR COUPLING EFFECT IN FOUR-POINT BENDING TESTS OF ANGLE PLY LAMINATES

D. Wowk*, D. Thibaudeau, C. Marsden

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Royal Military College of Canada,
Kingston, Canada

* Corresponding author (diane.wowk@rmc.ca)

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1 General Introduction

The response of composite laminates to combined in-plane and out-of-plane fatigue loading can be evaluated using bending tests. However, there may be significant differences in the internal stress state that develops when different physical test configurations are used to apply identical load cases [1]. For example, in four-point bending of angle-ply laminates, a test fixture with fixed supports does not produce a stress state representative of a pure moment as expected. A complex stress state is induced due to the presence of shear coupling, showing that the method of load introduction can produce different internal stress distributions for the same externally applied loads. When coupon-size test specimens are used to predict the response of full size components, the method of load introduction and the boundary conditions must be represented correctly in order to generate comparable internal loading scenarios.

Research focused on bending tests for composite laminates in fatigue has mostly dealt with cross ply laminates which do not experience shear coupling [2]. The studies that consider angle ply laminates have focused on using four-point bending tests to predict the flexural stiffness [3] due to the assumption of pure bending stress in the central region of the specimen.

The current work uses three dimensional finite element simulations to predict the internal stress state when pure bending is applied to thin angle ply laminates. Three different methods of load application are considered; a directly applied moment and four-point bending using two different support conditions. The induced internal loads are quantified in relation to the externally applied loads

using the classical laminate theory (CLT). The effects of different ply angles and specimen width on the resulting internal stress states and the out-of-plane deflection are investigated.

2 Methodology

A 4-ply (+/- α)_s carbon-epoxy layup was simulated using the material properties presented in Table 1 and the commercial software ANSYS. The baseline sample dimensions were 120 x 15.88 x 2.36mm ($2c \times 2b \times h$). Each ply was individually represented using 4 higher order hexahedral elements through the thickness, and local coordinate systems were used to define ply angles between 0° and 90°. The three load cases considered are illustrated in Figure 1. Load case 1 consists of a pure moment (M_x) applied directly to the ends of the central region of the specimen ($2a = 50\text{mm}$). Load case 2 is a simply supported four-point bend configuration where vertical deflection is prevented across the ends of the specimen at the location of the supports. A prescribed displacement (Δ) was applied across the specimen width at a distance of 25mm from each support instead of an applied force so that the sample is prevented from twisting about its longitudinal axis. Load case 3 is also a four-point bend configuration, but contact was defined between the supporting and loading rollers. This simulation is more representative of an experimental test set-up, where the entire width of the sample may not necessarily remain in contact with the supports at all times. Rollers with a diameter of 5 mm were used to represent supports located 10mm from each free end, and loading points located 25mm from each support. The supports were constrained from movement in all directions, while a vertical displacement was prescribed to the upper rollers. A non-linear analysis was defined which included

large deflections and a coefficient of friction of 0.2 to represent a carbon-epoxy and Teflon interface. Symmetry is often used in contact analyses to reduce the computational time [4], but in this case, angle-ply laminates do not deform in a symmetrical manner and the entire geometry must be considered. Ply angles of 80° and 90° were not modeled using the contact load case due to convergence difficulties when simulating components with very low flexural stiffness.

For load case 1, the magnitude of the applied moment varied for each ply lay-up, such that a central deflection of 0.264 mm was produced. For load cases 2 and 3, the applied displacement (Δ) required to produce the same moment in the central region as load case 1 was determined. For each ply layup, the same magnitude of applied moment was used for all three load cases.

The magnitudes of the internal loads generated during the four point bend tests were quantified using the classical laminate theory (CLT). The CLT is able to predict the state of stress and strain for each ply when an unconstrained thin laminate is subject to in plane forces and moments. The values of the applied forces and moments were varied until the CLT predicted the same stress and strain distributions as the finite element simulations. The residual between the two sets of predicted results was minimized using both stress and strain values within each ply at the center of the specimen.

Specimen widths of 5mm, 7.94mm, 15.88mm and 32mm were simulated for all three load cases. A [20/-20]_s laminate was used for the width study as this layup produced the largest reduction in vertical deflection between a pure moment and a four-point bend setup.

3 Simulation Results

3.1 Ply Angle Study

For load case 1, the application of a pure moment caused the samples to twist about their longitudinal axis (κ_{xy}) for all ply angles except for 0°

and 90°. The contours of vertical deflection also indicate a “saddle” shape (κ_y) where the centre deflects less than the edges. Figure 2 a) shows the overall deformed shape for a ply angle of 20° that has been magnified to show the twist as well as the vertical deflection of -0.264 mm at the center. Figure 2 b) shows that for the simply supported four-point bend configuration (load case 2) the twisting is completely prevented by the boundary conditions, and the vertical deflection at the centre is reduced to -0.168 mm relative to the supports. Figure 3 shows that for the contact model (load case 3), twisting is restricted by the rollers, but the contours of the VonMises stress show an uneven distribution of pressure under the loading points. This indicates that a very small twist occurs as the coupon is free to lift off the rollers. As a result, the deflection at the centre is -0.184 mm, which is larger than for the simply supported case.

The vertical deflection at the centre of the specimen is plotted in Figure 4 for all three load cases and ply angles between 0° and 90°. Ply angles of 0° and greater than 60° show minimal difference in the central deflection between a pure moment and the four-point bend cases while the maximum difference occurred at a ply angle of 20°. For all ply angles, the contact model predicted larger vertical deflections than the simply supported model. The decrease in the vertical deflection with four-point bend tests results in a reduction in the normal stress in the material direction as seen in Figure 5. Comparisons between Figures 4 and 5 are discussed in detail in section 4.

The magnitude of the in-plane shear stress (τ_{xy}) can be used as an indication of how much twist develops within the specimens. Figure 6 shows that more in-plane shear stress occurs when the pure moment is applied, and the least amount occurs with simply supported four-point bending. The maximum values occur at a ply angle of 20°, while ply angles of 0° and greater than 60° produce little to no in-plane shear stress indicating that these lay-ups have less of a tendency to twist.

One of the reasons that four-point bend tests are often preferred over three-point bend tests, is the

assumption that the central portion of the specimen is free of out-of-plane shear loads. In the case of angle-ply composite laminates in four-point bending, this assumption is not true. As shown in Figure 7, out-of-plane shear stress (τ_{xz}) develops for both four point bend configurations in ply angles between 0° and 80° . A ply angle of 30° generates the largest out-of-plane shear stress.

3.2 Quantification of Induced Loading

The configuration of the four point bend tests prevented the twisting that would have occurred if the specimens were free to deform without constraint. The physical boundary conditions had the effect of introducing an internal torsion, M_{xy} into the specimen in the opposite direction to the naturally occurring twist. In addition, a moment M_y was induced by the supports due to the requirement for the supports to remain horizontal. This resulted in the bowing of the specimen along its longitudinal axis, as seen in Figure 8, to be restricted. The magnitudes of M_{xy} and M_y as a percentage of the applied bending moment M_x are shown in Figure 9 for both cases of four point bending. The other in-plane loads that can be predicted using the CLT were found to be negligible.

3.3 Study of Specimen Width

The vertical deflections (d) obtained from four-point bend tests can be used to experimentally determine the flexural stiffness (E_1^f) of a composite laminate using equation (1),

$$E_1^f = \frac{3Fa^2(c-a)}{2bh^3d} \quad (1)$$

where F is the total applied load, and a , b , h and c are defined in section 2 [3]. For a $[20/-20]_s$ laminate, the calculated flexural modulus approaches the theoretical value as the sample width decreases as evident in Figure 10. At a sample width of 5mm, the flexural modulus is calculated to within 7% of the theoretical value when using the

deflection results from the contact model. When the flexural stiffness was determined using results from the pure moment case, the results were within 8% of the theoretical value.

4 Discussion

In the bending of angle-ply laminates, different methods of load application and test configuration can result in significantly different internal stress states. In four-point bending it is typically assumed that the central part of the sample sees only a bending moment, but angle-ply laminates may also be subjected to torque and out-of-plane shear as shown in Figures 6 and 7. This phenomenon is not easily predicted using traditional methods such as the classical laminate theory as all loads directly applied and induced by deformation of the component must be known a priori. In addition, the classical laminate theory is not able to account for the out-of-plane shear stress as it occurs in the out of plane direction.

In pure bending, the bending-twist coupling effect in angle ply laminates cause a twist to occur, resulting in in-plane shear stress. The four-point bend setup restricts the twist, reduces the maximum in-plane shear stress and induces an out-of-plane shear stress (τ_{xz}) into the specimen. Figures 6 and 7 show that these effects are the most pronounced between 20° and 30° , as these are the lay ups that have the largest coupling between the twisting curvature and the applied moment M_x . The distribution of out-of-plane shear stress is shown along the entire length of the specimen for ply angles of 0° and 30° in Figure 11. For a 0° laminate, twisting is not induced and the out-of-plane shear shows maximums between the supports and the applied load, and a value close to zero in the central portion. This is the expected distribution for a four-point bend setup using an isotropic material or a cross ply laminate. For a ply angle of 30° , the out-of-plane shear stress appears to represent a distributed load case, with the magnitude of the out-of-plane shear stress reaching a maximum between the supports (25mm – 75 mm). While the magnitude of the shear stress appears insignificant when compared to the maximum normal stress, it

can be as much as 20% of the in-plane shear stress for the cases considered here. In addition, this shear stress is oriented in the out of plane direction, which is governed by the lower strength of the matrix. It is also an interlaminar stress which reaches a maximum between the two middle plies, and must be accounted for when considering delamination failure.

The difference in the internal stress state between a pure moment and four-point bending is the largest for the simply supported case. The contact model allows the specimen to slightly lift off the rollers, resulting in stress states that fall somewhere between the pure moment and the simply supported case. Figure 5 shows that the reduction in the maximum normal stress in the material direction (σ_1) is larger for the contact case, which appears to contradict the trends seen for the other stress results. This is because the maximum stress does not occur in the same plies for the three load cases. Pure moments see the largest fiber stress in the interior plies as the bending and twisting curvatures are additive, while being subtracted in the outer plies. When in 4 point bending, the twist is restricted causing little to no curvature about the longitudinal axis and the magnitude of the stress is dependent on the distance of the ply from the midplane. The outer plies see higher normal stresses in the material direction resulting in a linear distribution through the thickness of the laminate as seen in Figure 12.

The classical laminate theory can be used to quantify the induced internal in-plane loads, but it is not able to account for the out-of-plane loads. The largest internally generated loads occurred for a ply angle of 40° using the simply supported four point bend configuration. An applied moment of $M_x = 16.03\text{N}$ introduced a torsion of $M_{xy} = 5.87\text{N}$ and a bending moment of $M_y = 1.04\text{N}$. Note that the CLT describes applied moments in terms of a unit length. Figure 13 shows that when these moments are applied to an unconstrained sample, in effect representing the boundary conditions, the distribution of normal stress (σ_x) in the longitudinal direction closely follows that of the simply supported configuration. Differences up to 17% can

be attributed to the CLT not being able to account for the out of plane shear load. The CLT also assumes uniform loads and moments across the entire face of the sample which results in the inability to produce the constant vertical deflection at the support locations that is seen in the simply supported case.

When considering angle ply laminates in bending, the resulting vertical deflections may not be an accurate basis for calculating the flexural stiffness because the assumed stress state resulting from the application of a pure moment is not present. The constraints applied by the test apparatus restrict the deformation of the specimen resulting in an increased apparent stiffness, even though the actual stiffness matrix of the laminate has not changed. One way to reduce this effect is to use a complex test setup with supports that are allowed to rotate about the longitudinal axis of the specimen [3]. Another way is to decrease the specimen width, thus decreasing the amount of twist and induced in-plane shear stress. Comparing the distribution of the normal stress in the material direction between Figures 12 and 14 for widths of 15.88mm and 5mm respectively shows that the narrower geometry behaves more like it is in pure bending than the wider geometry. The calculated flexural modulus approaches the theoretical value as the sample width decreases as evident in Figure 10. Although a width of 5 mm may not be considered to be a thin laminate when compared to its thickness of 2.36 mm, reducing the sample width may still provide a more realistic prediction of the theoretical flexural stiffness. When dealing with angle ply laminates in practice however, it is the flexural stiffness that results from the boundary conditions and the method of load application that drives the behaviour. The variation in the apparent flexural stiffness as the width of the sample changes indicates that test results from an angle ply laminate may not be able to be scaled to full size geometry.

4 Conclusions

An examination of three methods of applying bending moments shows significant

differences in the generated stress state for angle-ply laminates. The physical constraints applied by the four-point bend setup induce additional internal loads which result in a stress state that is different from that of a pure moment. These results highlight the importance of a test setup that recreates the same stress state as what occurs in the in-service component. It was shown that the load application method has a smaller effect on the internal stress state when the width of the coupon was reduced. The calculated flexural modulus was also shown to depend on the width of the test sample, indicating that results from subsize specimens may not be directly scaled to represent full size components.

5 References

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Table 1: Material properties for CYCOM 5276-1 with 640-800 tape

E_{11}	150GPa
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	8GPa
$G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{13}$	4Gpa
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{13}$	0.25

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 1: a) Load case 1: pure moment, b) load case 2: simply supported four-point bend setup, c) load case 3: four-point bend setup using contact. Dimensions are in mm.

Fig. 2: Deformed shape and contours of vertical deflection for a ply angle of 20° when a) a pure moment is applied, b) when a simply supported four-point bend configuration is used.

Fig. 3: Deformed shape and contours of Von Mises stress for a ply angle of 20° using a four-point bend configuration with contact.

Fig. 6: Maximum in plane shear stress in the interior plies, for ply angles between 0° and 90°.

Fig. 4: Vertical deflection at the centre of the specimen for ply angles between 0° and 90°.

Fig. 7: Maximum out-of-plane shear stress for ply angles between 0° and 90°.

Fig. 5: Percentage change in the maximum normal stress in the material direction between a pure moment and the four-point bend tests.

Fig. 8: Internal loads generated by the four-point bend test.

Fig. 11: Out-of-plane shear stress along the length of the sample for ply angles of 0° and 30°. Values were taken along the midplane of the laminate.

Fig. 9: a) The induced internal torque, M_{xy} and b) the induced internal moment M_y as a percentage of the externally applied moment M_x .

Fig. 10: Flexural modulus calculated from predicted vertical deflections for a range of specimen widths.

Fig. 12: The normal stress in the material direction for a specimen width of 15.88 mm. The maximum stress occurs in the interior plies for the pure moment case and in the exterior plies for the four-point bending cases.

Fig. 13: Normal stress in the longitudinal direction (σ_x) through the thickness at the centre of the specimen. The comparison is between a simply supported 4-point bend set-up and an unconstrained sample subject to moments determined using the CLT for a ply angle of 40° .

Fig. 14: Maximum fibre stress for a specimen width of 5mm and ply angle of 20° .